

Mixed Reality Golf Putting: A Comparative Analysis of Golf Putting Performance in Real, Virtual, and Augmented Virtuality Environments

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Fig. 1: Visualizations of the conditions evaluated in the user study: a) Real world; b) Augmented Virtuality, where real-world elements are integrated via video-passthrough; and c) Virtual Reality, in which the real golf putter and ball are virtually represented. In all conditions a real tracked putter and golf ball were used as physical proxies. Additionally, d) depicts the VE used for simulating golf putting.

Abstract— Although immersive technologies hold enormous potential for enhancing sports training, existing systems encounter notable limitations. While fully immersive virtual reality (VR) systems can address constraints of physical training setups such as limited space or equipment, full VR environments often lack rich, realistic, and multisensory feedback often required for effective sports training. To address this gap, this work investigates skill-based sport training, particularly, golf putting, across the reality–virtuality continuum. We implemented a mixed reality (MR) putting simulator that combines real equipment (putter and golf ball) with a virtual training environment. Three training conditions were realized: (i) real-world putting, constrained by limited physical space; (ii) a VR putting, in which a real putter and ball are used but represented virtually within the virtual environment (VE); (iii) an augmented virtuality (AV) putting, which reveals the real putter, ball, and users’ limbs through a localized video-passthrough window, aiming to preserve users’ sense of embodiment and presence while enabling simulation of an unlimited putting area.

We conducted a pilot within-subjects experiment with 36 participants and found that the AV condition improved immediate putting performance, reduced task load, reduced perceived motion sickness, and increased user preference compared to the VR condition, while user’s sense of presence remained comparable to VR training. These findings indicate that AV offers a pragmatic “sweet spot” on the virtuality continuum, balancing the trade-off between sensory fidelity and training flexibility, offering valuable design insights for immersive sports training systems.

Index Terms—Mixed Reality, Virtual Reality, Augmented Virtuality, Golf Training.

1 INTRODUCTION

Advances in immersive technology such as virtual reality (VR) are transforming the way physical skill training can be conducted, enabling controlled, repeatable, and adaptable simulations of real-world tasks. Nowadays, VR training applications already span a wide variety of

disciplines [44], from endurance activities, such as cycling [26] and rowing [20], to more interactive skill-based disciplines, such as baseball batting [13], darts [7], and golf [5, 10, 16]. These applications highlight VR’s potential to deliver realistic scenarios and rich performance feedback while preserving safety and flexibility [44]. However, a fundamental challenge persists: fully immersive VR simulations often lack coherent multimodal sensory input, such as haptic and proprioceptive feedback, limiting physical performance and perception [5, 16, 17, 44]. In contrast, real-world training environments offer authentic sensory cues, but are typically limited by space, equipment availability, and limited dynamic feedback. This trade-off between sensory fidelity and immersive training flexibility creates a design gap: the more immersive and adaptable the virtual system, the greater the risk of compromising the authentic sensory and physical feedback required for effective skill acquisition in precision sports.

Mixed reality (MR) approaches, situated along Milgram’s reality–virtuality continuum [30], offer a promising way to navigate this trade-off. In particular, augmented virtuality (AV) along Milgram’s reality–

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virtuality continuum integrates elements of the physical world into predominantly virtual environments, blending virtual adaptability with real-world grounding while preserving the capability of a fully immersive system in simulating large unlimited space. Prior work in non-sport domains suggests that revealing physical objects or body parts within VR can reduce task load, enhance performance, and support embodiment [6, 42, 43]. Yet, despite encouraging evidence in abstract tasks such as typing [6] and object manipulation [42, 43], the potential of AV for sports training, especially in fine-motor, precision-based skills sport such as golf putting remains largely unexplored. In this work, we explore immersive sport training for precision sport across the reality–virtuality continuum. Specifically, we focused on a case study in immersive golf putting, an ideal context for examining interfaces in skill-based sports because it relies heavily on precision, haptic feedback, and spatial perception [25, 31], and stands to benefit from immersive technology, which can greatly enhance accessibility of golf training by simulating large unbounded space.

We designed, implemented, and compared three golf putting training scenarios as shown in Figure 1: i) RW: where participants putt using a physical putter and golf ball on a real putting surface, however, the area of the putting surface is constrained by limited physical space; ii) VR: where participants use the same physical putter and ball, but interact within a fully virtual environment (VE) that displays virtual counterparts of the real objects with the VE unbounded by physical constraint; and iii) AV: where the virtual environment is enriched by selectively revealing the physical putter, ball, and the user’s feet. Moreover, in AV, even when the physical ball reaches the boundary of the training ground, the virtual ball can continue to roll, enabling uninterrupted practice, extended scenario design, and skill development beyond the constraints of physical space. We conducted a controlled within-subjects pilot study with 36 participants who completed repeated putting tasks. We demonstrate that users achieved higher putting performance, reported lower perceived task load, and lower perceived motion sickness in AV putting than in VR. Finally, we discuss the design implications of these results for practitioners developing immersive training systems, highlighting how AV can be leveraged to balance sensory fidelity with immersive flexibility in precision sports contexts.

In summary, the contributions of this paper include:

- Novel high-fidelity immersive golf putting training systems across the reality–virtuality continuum, demonstrating how precise, high-performance skill training can be achieved in limited physical space using both VR and AV.
- Empirical evaluation of users’ putting performance, user experience, and user perception in RW, VR, and AV environments through a within-subjects user study.
- Discussions and design insights for building immersive training systems that balance physical realism with the scalability and flexibility of virtual environments.

2 RELATED WORK

2.1 VR for Sports Training

Immersive VR simulations have become a popular tool for training movement skills in sport [32, 36, 44]. A systematic review by Neuman et al. on earlier adoption (1997-2016) outlined that VR training was mostly applied to disciplines with activities primarily involving gross motor and endurance skills such as cycling, running, rowing, and weightlifting [32]. More recently, studies on VR training also include fine motor skills activities like darts, table tennis, baseball, and golf putting [44]. VR training has some notable strengths, such as cost effectiveness, repeatability, and control over the training environment [8, 36]. The effectiveness of learning visuomotor skills through VR training interventions has been shown for, e.g., baseball batting [13], table tennis [33], and other disciplines, including some that require precision skills [36, 44]. In contrast, the effectiveness of VR training could not be confirmed for disciplines such as dart throwing [7], raising

questions about its effectiveness in tasks that require precise spatial perception and physical interaction.

A key limitation to current VR sport training systems is the fidelity of the simulation. For a successful skill transfer, the VR intervention should accurately represent the real-world interaction [14, 16]. In their recent review, Witte et al. concluded that not all sensory stimuli from real sports can be replicated in VR with current technology [44]. For example, most predominately, a lack of haptic feedback and tactile realism could lead to differences in perception and motor execution [5, 17, 44]. An approach to address this issue is to introduce physical elements that mirror the properties of real-world sports equipment [10]. Multiple studies successfully applied real equipment or properties to enhance haptic feedback in virtual sports simulations, e.g., baseball batting [13], table tennis [45], and skiing [19, 34]. However, while these haptic enhancements improved physical fidelity, they did not fully resolve other perceptual gaps, such as limited self-representation [10]. To complement this, in our interface design, we explore VR and AV training that enable users to perceive their lower body either through a virtual avatar or via video passthrough along with providing real-world haptic feedback by using physical sport equipments.

2.2 Golf Putting in VEs

The primary objective in golf is to hit a ball into a designated hole using the minimum number of strokes. Putting refers to the strokes taken on the “putting green”, where the ball rolls toward the hole along the short grass. Specialized equipment called a “putter” is used. As putting plays a critical role in scoring, often accounting for a significant portion of total strokes [4], it presents a relevant and controlled interaction for precision-based studies.

Several prior studies already investigated golf putting in VR focusing on aspects such as simulation validity, putting performance, and perception [5, 10, 12, 16], typically integrating a real putter to enhance haptics. Harris et al. evaluated physical and psychological fidelity, as well as construct validity of a VR golf putting simulation by comparing performance and experience between real-world and VR putting [16]. While their results support the validity of the simulation and indicate that VR systems can represent real putting performance [16], some differences between real-world and VR putting were still apparent, e.g., the radial error was higher in the VR setting, and the correlation between real-world and VR performance was only moderate. These differences indicate that key sensory channels such as full physical fidelity and accurate self-representation were still missing, limiting equivalence with real-world performance [16]. Pushing the boundaries of conventional putting, Godse et al. used the capabilities of VR to test a perceptual training intervention. They found that VR training with larger holes and balls improved putting performance in a post-test and worsened after training with smaller ones [12]. These findings emphasize how subtle differences in visual representation between the real world and VR can influence performance. Brock et al. reported differences in postural control and swing kinematics between real world and VR putting [5]. By additionally introducing a real golf ball into the VE during virtual putting, the swing kinematics became more similar to real-world putting. However, the differences in posture control remained, suggesting that only increasing haptic realism alone is not sufficient to achieve motor equivalence [5].

Prior studies indicate that even VR putting simulations incorporating a real putter and golf ball do not fully replicate the multimodal feedback necessary for real-world performance. Our work extends VR simulation for precision sports such as golf by combining AV visualization and physical components to enhance embodiment and reduce the gap between virtual and real-world motor behavior, making a further step towards more ecologically valid and transferable VR training for precision skill-based sport.

2.3 Immersive Experiences on the Virtuality Continuum

The framework of Milgram and Kishino defines a “Virtuality continuum” between real and virtual environments [30]. On the one side, Augmented Reality (AR) overlays virtual elements on a mostly real environment. On the opposite side, AV enhances a predominantly virtual

environment by integrating real-world elements. Together, they define the term MR for systems on this continuum that merge real and virtual worlds [30]. Following Skarbez et al.’s revision, conventional VR sits within the broader MR [38]. References to the MR manifestation in this work follow the updated definition from Skarbez et al. Moreover, to clearly distinguish the primary environment and the role of real-world visual information, we adopt Milgram and Kishino’s original definitions when referring to VR and AV [30]. In one of the designs of our system, the environment is primarily virtual, with real-world elements (e.g., the putter, golf ball, and user’s body) selectively revealed via localized video-passthrough. We therefore use the term AV rather than AR, as AR typically refers to a predominantly real environment augmented with virtual content. This distinction situates our approach more precisely along the virtuality continuum.

Contrary to putting simulations in purely virtual environments, AR-based systems, such as the putting swing guide presented by Geisen et al. offer promising results to enhance golf putting training [11]. However, such systems remain constrained to real-world environments, such as the golf course and still requires large practice green for putting. In contrast, AV allows simulating unlimited putting area in a VE while still leveraging real-world cues. While there is limited work investigating various human factors of AV for sport, in non-sport domains, several studies demonstrate how AV can support realistic interactions [43], improve perceived presence [42], and reduce task load [6]. Villegas et al. showed that segmenting a view of the user’s real hands and real physical objects into a VE directly addresses the lack of tactile and visual grounding in VR, improving user’s perceived sense of presence, and overall quality of experience of a gamified training task [42]. More recently, Waldow et al. extended this by introducing full-body video-passthrough embodiment, which helps close the gap in self-representation, an aspect often missing in VR sports simulations [43]. Our AV interface build on these prior findings by integrating user’s real hands and lower limbs into the putting VE aiming to transfer these positive effects in reducing task load, enhancing presence, and improving user preferences in the domain of precision-based sport training.

3 IMPLEMENTATION

Based on prior work on virtual golf putting training described in Section 2, we formulated the following design goals (DG) which guided the development of our golf putting training system.

DG1: Simulation accuracy. The system should accurately simulate a putt (e.g., the trajectory and final resting position of the golf ball) to facilitate skill transfer from VR to real-world performance.

DG2: Haptics and tactile feedback. The training system should provide users with realistic tactile and haptic feedback [10].

DG3: Self-representation. The training system should visualize the putter, ball, and the user’s hands and feet to strengthen presence and foster a clear sense of self-representation [43].

3.1 System Setup

MR HMD. To implement the putting simulation, we used an MR HMD and a device for tracking the golf putter. The Meta Quest 3 was chosen for its high-quality color passthrough and its controllers, which can be used for putter tracking [28].

Tracked Golf Putter. We used a a Sik Sho C-Series golf putter, a standard putter with a length of 86 cm. To achieve DG2, the right controller of Meta Quest 3 was used to track the putter during the putting simulation. A custom 3D-printed attachment [15] was used to mount the controller to the putter shaft. This attachment relied on a combination of friction and a clamping mechanism for secure fixation. The placement was chosen close to the grip to not obstruct the player’s view of the putter head while putting. In addition, the attachment was fixed facing the putter head because it allowed for the best balance. The attachment closely resembles the prototype developed by Franzluebbbers and Johnsen [10]. Including the controller and the attachment, the total weight of the putter was 700 g. The putter with attached controller is shown in 2. Furthermore, the putter head of the Sik Sho putter was

Fig. 2: The golf putter (a) with Meta Quest 3 controller mounted by 3D-printed attachment (b).

3D-scanned using the Kiri Engine app [23] on an Apple iPhone 14 Pro to create a realistic virtual putter model. This mounting method is also compatible with other putters, only requiring changes in the putter’s visual and parameters of the simulation physics model.

Physical Training Area. A real-world putting environment with bounded space was established using an appropriate surface to approximate the characteristics of a real golf putting green. A specialized golf putting training aid, PuttView M12¹, was selected. It consists of a 12 feet (3.67 m) by 8 feet (2.44 m) platform with carpet like a real golf green turf and a regulation-size golf cup [41]. The platform was chosen for the evaluation due to its flat surface (default setting) and carpet, which enables authentic putting interactions and allows real golf balls to be played into a physical hole. Moreover, the system can track the ball that is played on the platform with an overhead camera. The ball tracking feature was used to obtain the putting performance metrics for later evaluation. The use of a flat surface was an intentional simplification for the initial investigation for evaluating different interface designs, as introducing slope variations would add an additional independent variable and substantially increase evaluation complexity. Moreover, flat or near-flat putts are also encountered in real golf practice, making this setup a reasonable approximation for evaluating immersive putting training accuracy in relation to DG1. The physical training setup is illustrated in Figure 3 (a).

Calibration. Two types of calibration are required for the system and user study: putter calibration, to ensure the virtual putter accurately reflects the pose and motion of the real putter, and world anchoring, to ensure alignment between the virtual and physical ball positions. Putter calibration followed a manual hand-eye calibration process. The resulting calibration pose was saved and reloaded with each simulation startup. World anchoring of the application is achieved by placing two spatial anchors on the platform using Meta’s Spatial Anchor SDK [27]. The application maintains consistent spatial alignment between the virtual and physical environments using these fixed reference points.

Software. The system supports training in VR, AV, and real-world putting modes. The AV and VR components were implemented using the Unity game engine (version 2022.3.51f) [40].

3.2 Putting Simulation

Overview. To support DG1, we developed a virtual environment that realistically simulates golf putting through physics-based ball behavior. A visual comparison between the VE and the real-world putting platform is shown in 3. The virtual golf hole and ball were modeled to match the regulation size: 10.8 cm and 4.267 cm in diameter, respectively. A digital twin of the real putter was created from its 3D scan using Blender to represent the putter in the VE. The system is compatible with any sloped green mesh, as real putting greens are rarely perfectly flat. However, it is important to notice that for the

¹<https://www.puttview.com/products/indoor/moving-series/>

Fig. 3: (a) The physical putting environment with a bounded space ($3.67m \times 2.44m$), and (b) the virtual putting environment offering an unbounded simulation area.

user experiment, a flat surface was modeled in order to isolate sensory fidelity from environmental variability.

Physics Simulation. Unity’s built-in physics engine (NVIDIA PhysX) was used to simulate rigid-body dynamics with a time step of $1/180$ s. The Meta Quest 3 ran at 90 Hz to ensure synchronization and smooth 90 fps rendering. A virtual putter face was aligned with the real putter via manual hand-eye calibration. Ball launches were detected using a trigger collider on the virtual putter face, which triggered a launch upon contact with the virtual ball.

Putter Launch Vector. The velocity of the putter head at impact was obtained by the first derivative of the mounted Quest 3 controllers position with respect to time. Since the Quest 3 controller position is not required to update every physics timestep, filtering was necessary for distinct positions. Empirical validation with a Foresight Sports GCQuad launch monitor confirmed that speed was most reliable when derived from the last significant movement, while direction was more stable when averaged over six time steps [9].

Ball Physics Modeling. The ball’s launch velocity was computed using the principle of momentum conservation and the coefficient of restitution to model the launch as an inelastic collision [3]. The coefficient of restitution was determined empirically. The physics model also included drag coefficients for the ball and friction coefficients for the green based on the physics materials of the Unity engine. These parameters, together with the coefficient of restitution, were calibrated using a Foresight GCQuad launch monitor with the PuttView M12 and Sik Sho putter setup. To improve robustness, launches were disabled for 1.5 s after impact, and the ball was stopped when velocity dropped below 0.01 m/s. Despite its simplicity, this model reproduced realistic ball launches and trajectories. Across 1,080 trials evaluated in the user study, the mean miss distance difference between the simulated (Quest 3) and real (PuttView) putts was computed to validate the simulation accuracy. Because the physical green has boundaries while the simulation is unbounded, we restricted this comparison to putts with a miss distance under 0.4 m, avoiding distortions from rebounds or boundary effects. For these putts, the mean miss distance difference per participant was 0.028 m (SD = 0.057), with a mean absolute difference of 0.046 m (SD = 0.040). These values indicate that the simulation closely matches the real-world putt outcomes. Importantly, these positional discrepancies were only used to validate the simulation; no error corrections were applied to the experimental dataset. A detailed description of the simulation accuracy estimation process is available in the supplementary materials.

3.3 Self-Representation

To support DG3 in enhancing users’ sense of self-representation during virtual training, the VR and AV modes employ distinct strategies for visualizing the user’s hands and lower limbs.

Self-representation in AV. The Passthrough API provided by the Meta SDK [27] was utilized to create a fixed rectangular window (0.75×0.50 m) around the ball’s start position, revealing a view into the real world. The size was chosen to reveal enough real sensory cues for the putting interaction while maintaining presence. To ensure a seamless transition between the VE and the passthrough area, a custom Unity shader was implemented using a UV-based rectangular edge fade. This shader blurred the boundary of the passthrough cutout, reducing visual discontinuities. In addition, Quest 3’s hand-tracking feature was configured to render the user’s hands with a passthrough material. Together, these components enabled the AV mode of the simulation, blending the real-world view of the putter, ball, and user’s feet and hands into the VE. An illustration of the passthrough cutout is shown in Figure 1 (b).

Self-representation in VR. To support a coherent experience in the VR mode, a simple lower-body avatar was used to visualize the user’s legs and feet and provide stance-related cues during putting. This visual aid served as a reference for body alignment, which is an important component of putting technique. Due to a current limitation in the Meta SDK, the Inside-Out Body Tracking (IOBT) feature is incompatible with the simultaneous use of hand and controller tracking (multimodal tracking) [27]. As a result, full-body tracking could not be implemented. Instead, the position of the avatar was estimated based on the HMD location and aligned with the putt direction in the VE. While this approach does not capture precise foot placement, it was sufficient to convey stance orientation and relative positioning, which were the primary cues required for this study. No avatar was shown in AV to avoid conflicts with video-based self-representation. The lower-body avatar is visualized in Figure 1 (c).

4 USER STUDY

To evaluate the training system and different putt training modes, we conducted a within-subject experiment with golf putting tasks in three conditions as shown in Figure 1: i) real world, ii) AV, and iii) VR. All conditions used the same physical putter and ball for realistic haptic feedback, differing only in the visualization of the user’s self-representation and the putting environment. The study design and hypotheses were guided by the following research question (RQ):

RQ: *Can AV visualization bridge the gap between RW and VR conditions by retaining the immersive flexibility of VR while reintroducing task-relevant sensory cues to enhance putting performance, reduce task load, and enhance user experience in precision-based sports simulations?*

4.1 Hypotheses

Although the ultimate goal of VR or AV training is to approach real-world performance, prior studies indicate that even high-fidelity VR simulations with real putters and golf balls do not fully replicate the multimodal sensory feedback available in real-world putting, including proprioceptive and postural cues [5, 10, 16]. Limitations of current VR head-mounted displays, including restricted field of view, imperfect hand and body tracking, and reduced haptic fidelity, further constrain motor equivalence [24]. Based on these factors, we hypothesize that:

H1 Participants will exhibit significantly better *putting performance* in RW compared to AV and VR.

Similarly, MR approaches that reveal real objects (AV) have been shown to support embodiment, reduce task load, and enhance user experience in other domains [6, 42, 43]. Building on these prior findings, we formulate the following hypotheses:

H2 Participants will have significantly better *putting performance* in AV compared to VR, as AV preserves real-world visual cues of the putter and limbs, supporting embodiment and sensorimotor alignment [42, 43].

H3 Participants will report significantly higher *task load* and worse overall user preference in VR compared to RW and AV, consistent with studies showing increased cognitive demand and reduced embodiment in fully virtual settings [6, 42].

H4 Participants will report a significantly higher *sense of presence* and *perceived putting realism* in AV than VR, as AV integrates real hands and body parts to enhance embodiment and presence [42, 43].

4.2 Tasks

In each condition, participants performed ten straight putts from a fixed distance of 2.13 m (7 ft) using a real putter and ball on a flat surface. Straight putts were chosen to maintain experimental control and isolate a single representative interaction, avoiding the added complexity of slopes or breaks. The distance of 2.13 m provided an appropriate task difficulty: challenging enough for novices but not trivial for experienced golfers. Previous data indicate one-putt probabilities of 32% for amateurs and 47% for more skilled players at this distance [4], with success likely higher on flat putts. Additionally, prior evaluations suggest that distances of 1–3 m can be perceived accurately in HMDs like the Meta Quest 3 [35], supporting its use across real and virtual conditions.

4.3 Metrics

Workload. Workload was assessed using the NASA Task Load Index (NASA-TLX) [18], which measures mental, physical, and temporal demand, as well as performance, effort, and frustration. The original 1–100 scale (in 5-point increments) was adapted to an 11-point Likert scale, with anchors labeled 0 = perfect to 100 = failure for performance and 0 = very low to 100 = very high for the remaining dimensions.

Perceived Presence. Users' perceived presence was measured with the Igroup Presence Questionnaire (IPQ) [37], which assesses three dimensions: spatial presence, involvement, and experienced realism, along with a general presence item. Each item was rated on a 7-point Likert scale ranging from 0 (fully disagree) to 6 (fully agree).

Motion Sickness. Participants reported cybersickness symptoms using the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (SSQ) [22], which includes 16 items rated on a 4-point Likert scale (0 = none, 3 = severe). Following Kennedy et al., responses were aggregated into nausea, oculomotor, and disorientation subscales, along with a total score.

Mean Absolute Miss Distance. Mean absolute miss distance (ball center to hole center in meters) was used to quantify putting accuracy. Miss distances were measured both physically, using the PuttView ball tracking system, and virtually, using the Quest 3 simulation data. Because the physical measurements were constrained by the platform boundaries, mean absolute miss distances were compared only between the AV and VR conditions, with the filtered physical data used to estimate the simulation accuracy of the AV and VR modes.

Putts Holed Percentage. Putting performance was quantified in part by the percentage of putts holed across the ten putts in each condition. This metric provides a direct measure of success and complements the assessment of spatial accuracy. Aggregated metrics were calculated per participant per condition, and generalized linear mixed models (GLMMs) were fitted on individual putts for deeper insights. Since the ball-tracking data is constrained by the physical space, the percentage of holed putts serves as the primary metric for comparing putting performance across RW and VEs.

Post-study Questionnaire. Overall preference and perceived realism of interactions in VEs were assessed using a custom post-experiment questionnaire, designed to evaluate users' perceptions of various aspects of realism during putting tasks. A copy of the questionnaire is provided in the supplementary material.

4.4 Materials

The study was conducted at Viewlicity GmbH in a dedicated testing room with a PuttView M12 moving platform set to a flat surface to isolate sensory fidelity. The surface was regularly vacuumed to maintain consistent rolling conditions and green speed. Lighting was controlled via two overhead LED panels. The Meta Quest 3, used in standalone mode, enabled the immersive AV and VR conditions. A standard Sik Sho C-Series putter with a 3D-printed attachment [15] held the Quest 3 controller for all conditions, including RW, ensuring tracking consistency. Controlled variables such as platform, lighting, blinds, putter,

ball, and hole positions ensured uniform conditions across participants and experimental setups. More details on the custom application and hardware are provided in Section 3.1.

4.5 Procedure

At our institution, formal ethics committee approval is not required for user studies that do not involve identifiable ethical risks. Prior to conducting the study, we completed an internal ethics screening questionnaire assessing potential concerns such as participants' ability to provide informed consent, involvement of vulnerable populations, use of deception, physiological or psychological stress, invasive procedures, collection of non-anonymizable personal data, or other ethically sensitive factors. As none of these conditions applied to our study, consultation with the institutional ethics committee was not required.

To minimize order effects, condition sequences were counterbalanced using a balanced Latin square ($n = 3$). Participants were informed about the study purpose, procedures, and motion sickness risks, and provided written consent prior to the study. They received a brief introduction to putting, including a demonstration of a standard stroke, followed by a short practice session with a standard putter (different from the one used in the trials) on the real green. This familiarization phase was conducted solely in the RW setting, on the PuttView M12 platform, where participants were allowed up to three practice putts. The putter used was similar in size to the experimental putter but did not have the attached controller. Participants were explicitly instructed not to stand near the designated start position for the study trials, and this phase was only intended to provide a basic feel for putting mechanics and green speed, without contributing to actual experimental learning. As such, the familiarization was minimal and unlikely to bias performance in the subsequent RW, VR, or AV conditions. Participants then began either the RW condition or one of the immersive conditions (VR or AV using Meta Quest 3). In the VR and AV conditions, a brief calibration ensured alignment of the virtual ball and putter with their physical counterparts on the PuttView platform. The RW condition used the same putter with the attached Quest 3 controller for consistency. Participants completed ten putts per condition, with the experimenter resetting the ball between putts, and no time limits was imposed for finishing the tasks. After each condition, participants filled out a post-condition questionnaire, and breaks were offered to minimize SSQ carryover; calibration was re-checked before each virtual condition.

4.6 Participants

Overview. A total of 37 participants were recruited, with one excluded due to incomplete data, resulting in a final sample of 36 (15 female, 21 male). All participants had normal or corrected-to-normal vision and no conditions affecting stance. Participants were recruited from the University of Hamburg. In line with institutional guidelines, participants who are students received class credits. The sample size was chosen to align with prior immersive sports training studies using within-subjects designs. For example, Harris et al. [16] evaluated VR golf putting with 36 participants across expertise levels, and Franzluebbers and Johnsen [10] reported significant effects with 20 participants.

Age and Handedness. Participants' ages were distributed as follows: 18–24 years ($N=13$), 25–34 years ($N=17$), 35–44 years ($N=5$), and 55–64 years ($N=1$). Most participants were right-handed ($N=34$); two were left-handed but used a right-handed putter. Because the setup was designed for right-handed use, participants were recruited only if comfortable putting right-handed.

VR and Golf Experience. On a 0–6 scale (0 = less than once a year, 6 = more than once a week), average VR usage was 4.33 ($SD = 1.74$). Golf frequency averaged 1.22 ($SD = 1.78$), and putting practice 1.69 ($SD = 2.20$).

Putting skill. Participants rated their putting ability on a 0–4 scale (0 = beginner, 4 = expert), yielding an average of 1.14 ($SD = 1.29$). Seventeen participants reported no experience or skill, while 19 reported at least some.

Fig. 4: NASA-TLX results for each dimension and the total score per condition including Wilcoxon signed-rank post hoc test results (significance codes: *** ≤ 0.001 , ** ≤ 0.01 and * ≤ 0.05).

5 RESULTS

In this section, we highlight the analysis of the quantitative measures. Tables listing full numerical results of all measures can be found in the supplementary materials.

5.1 Objective Putting Performance

Putt Holed Percentage (Physical Tracking): RW > VR; AV > VR. To assess the *holed percentage*, a series of GLMMs with a logit link function were fitted on individual putts to examine the effect of condition on the likelihood of holed putts. Covariates from the pre-questionnaire were included to account for potential confounding variables. The final best-fitting model included condition, putt index (centered, to capture within-condition learning across the ten putts), putting skill and putting training frequency (both z-standardized), their interactions with condition, and a random intercept for participant (model formula: $Holed \sim Condition * (PuttingSkill_z + PuttingTrainingFrequency_z) + PuttIndex_c + (1|ParticipantId)$). The remaining covariates VR experience and golf training frequency were dropped because they neither improved fit nor reached significance. Model checks indicated no overdispersion. Fixed effects explained 13% of variance (marginal $R^2 = 0.13$), increasing to 16% when including the random intercept (conditional $R^2 = 0.16$). Significant main effects were observed for condition ($\chi^2(2) = 7.72, p = 0.021$), putt index ($\chi^2(1) = 19.44, p < 0.001$), and putting skill ($\chi^2(1) = 15.29, p < 0.001$), plus interactions condition \times putting skill ($\chi^2(2) = 9.5, p = 0.009$) and condition \times putting training frequency ($\chi^2(2) = 7.71, p = 0.021$). As shown in Figure 5 (b), post hoc EMMs (response scale) and odds ratios (OR; Holm-adjusted p -values, Bonferroni-adjusted 95% CIs) indicated lower holed odds in VR relative to RW (RW vs. VR: OR = 1.50, 95% CI [1.02, 2.21], $p = 0.0365$) and relative to AV (VR vs. AV: OR = 0.70, 95% CI [0.48, 1.02], $p = 0.0470$); RW vs. AV was not significant ($p = 0.7715$). Marginal holed probabilities (EMMs; 95% CI) were: RW = 0.575 [0.512, 0.635], VR = 0.474 [0.415, 0.534], AV = 0.563 [0.503, 0.622].

Absolute Miss Distance (Virtual Simulation): VR > AV. For each participant and condition (VR, AV), the ten putts were aggregated as *mean miss distance* (Euclidean error, including holed putts as zero) and *holed percentage*. Eleven putts (1.53%) were removed (3 SD rule) due to rare controller glitches, resulting in $N = 36$ participants and 709 putts for analysis. To assess the *miss distance*, a series of GLMMs were fitted

predicting the raw miss distance on the unaggregated putts. Model comparisons indicated that a log-link Tweedie GLMM with fixed effects for condition, putting skill (z-standardized), and golf training frequency (z-standardized), plus a random intercept for participant, provided the best fit (model formula: $MissDistance \sim Condition + PuttingSkill_z + GolfTrainingFrequency_z + (1|ParticipantId)$). The Tweedie distribution with a log-link function accommodates the positive-skewed and zero-inflated nature of the miss distance. The remaining covariates were dropped because they did not improve model fit or reached significance. The model diagnostics did not show evidence of misfit. Fixed effects explained 33% of the variance (marginal $R^2 = 0.33$), increasing to 43% when including the random intercept (conditional $R^2 = 0.43$). A Wald chi-square test revealed significant main effects of condition ($\chi^2(1) = 9.25, p = 0.002$), putting skill ($\chi^2(1) = 5.60, p = 0.018$), and golf training frequency ($\chi^2(1) = 6.71, p = 0.010$). Post hoc EMMs on the response scale (geometric means under the log link) yielded a VR vs. AV miss distance ratio of 1.29 (95% CI [1.09, 1.52], Holm-adjusted $p = 0.0024$), indicating higher miss distances in VR. Marginal miss distances (EMMs; 95% CI) were: VR = 0.39 [0.33, 0.47], AV = 0.30 [0.26, 0.36]. Figure 5 (a) shows a visual comparison of the mean miss distance between the VR and AV conditions.

5.2 Perceived Simulator Sickness

The SSQ [22] was administered as a pre-measure before starting the study and a post-measure after each condition. For subsequent analysis, pre-measurements were subtracted from post-condition measurements to evaluate differences as a relative score according to the guideline of Bimberg et al. [2, 22].

SSQ: VR > AV > RW. The mean difference in the total SSQ score was -3.32 ($SD = 10.49$) after the RW condition, 4.57 ($SD = 12.49$) after the VR condition, and 0.83 ($SD = 14.2$) after the AV condition. Shapiro-Wilk test suggests that the SSQ scores were not normally distributed ($p < .05$). Friedman tests were conducted on the total SSQ score and the three subscales, revealing significant main effects of condition on the four measures. Post hoc comparisons using Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm correction showed that VR resulted in significantly higher nausea ($W = 5.0, p = 0.002, r = 0.54$) and disorientation ($W = 0.0, p = 0.002, r = 0.60$) than RW. Moreover, VR resulted in a significantly higher total oculomotor score than RW ($W = 1.0, p = 0.0002, r = 0.64$) and AV ($W = 141.0, p = 0.016, r = 0.358$). Similarly, VR leads to higher overall SSQ score than RW ($W = 6.0, p = 0.00015, r = 0.67$)

Fig. 5: (a). Mean miss distance of the virtual ball per condition. (b). Holed percentage of the physical ball per condition. Diamonds + white bars = model EMMs ($\pm 95\%$ CI) for an average participant (covariates at their means, random effects = 0); stars = Holm-adjusted post hoc (significance codes: *** ≤ 0.001 , ** ≤ 0.01 and * ≤ 0.05).

and AV ($W = 163, p = 0.031, r = 0.38$). In both oculomotor ($W = 5.5, p = 0.009, r = 0.41$) and total score ($W = 20, p = 0.008, r = 0.46$), AV resulted in significantly higher score. Differences in other subscales or pair-wise comparisons did not yield significant results.

5.3 Perceived Task Load

Mental Demand: VR > RW & AV. Shapiro-Wilk tests showed that the NASA-TLX questionnaire scores were not normally distributed. A Friedman test revealed a significant effect of condition on mental demand ($\chi^2(2) = 18.35, p = 0.0001, W = 0.25$). Post hoc comparisons using pairwise Wilcoxon signed-rank tests with Holm correction showed that VR has significantly higher perceived mental demand than RW ($W = 61, p = 0.0007, r = 0.62$) and AV ($W = 406, p = 0.005, r = 0.52$), but not between RW and AV.

Physical Demand: VR > RW. Furthermore, a significant effect of the condition on physical demand was indicated by a Friedman test ($\chi^2(2) = 13.77, p = 0.001, W = 0.19$). Post hoc comparisons showed that VR has significant higher perceived physical demand than RW ($W = 56, p = 0.02, r = 0.51$).

Performance: VR > RW & AV. Furthermore, a Friedman test on the performance dimension indicated a significant effect ($\chi^2(2) = 15.54, p = 0.0004, W = 0.22$). Post hoc comparisons revealed VR has significantly worse perceived performance than RW ($W = 478, p = 0.006, r = 0.52$) and AV ($W = 104.5, p = 0.009, r = 0.51$).

Frustration: VR > RW. For the frustration dimension, a Friedman test indicated a significant effect ($\chi^2(2) = 8.47, p = 0.01, W = 0.12$). Post hoc comparisons showed VR leads to significantly higher frustration than RW ($W = 70, p = 0.01, r = 0.47$).

Others. Differences in the total score, the temporal demand, and the effort dimensions were not significant.

5.4 Perceived Presence

The IPQ [37] for perceived presence was measured for the VR and AV conditions. The scores were calculated by reversing the answers in the SP2, INV3, and REAL1 questions as described by the authors [21]. Since the scores of the three subscales were normally distributed, paired t-tests were performed. Differences in the scores of the three subscales were not significant: spatial presence ($t(35) = 0.58, p = 0.57, d = 0.1$), involvement ($t(35) = 0.55, p = 0.59, d = 0.09$), and realism ($t(35) = -0.13, p = 0.9, d = -0.02$). Shapiro-Wilk tests indicated that the results for general presence were not normally distributed, therefore a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was performed without a significant result ($W = 107, p = 0.77, r = 0.09$).

5.5 Perceived Realism and User Preferences

The first three questions of the custom post-experiment questionnaire were about perceived realism. On a seven-point Likert scale from strongly disagree (= 0) to strongly agree (= 6), participants were asked

Fig. 6: Post-experiment questionnaire: “Which condition do you think allowed for better direction/distance control of the ball?”

to rate whether VR and AV conditions felt like a realistic putting experience. The mean of the question “VR felt like a realistic putting experience” was 3.41 ($SD = 1.63$) and 4.25 ($SD = 1.36$) for the same question regarding AV. Since a Shapiro-Wilk test indicated that the responses were not distributed normal, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test was calculated, resulting in a significant difference ($W = 120, p = 0.01, r = 0.45$). Participants were also asked whether the weight of the putter was disturbing (seven-point Likert scale). The mean was 0.5 ($SD = 1$), indicating that the majority of participants disagreed that the weight of the putter was disturbing. Moreover, the next pair of questions targeted distance and directional control while putting on a seven-point Likert scale between VR (= 0) and AV (= 6). The resulting mean for distance control was 4 ($SD = 1.99$) and for direction control 4.28 ($SD = 1.99$). The responses were not normally distributed. A Wilcoxon signed-rank test indicated that there was no significant difference between responses regarding distance and directional control ($W = 38.5, p = 0.22, r = 0.22$). Nonetheless, as shown in Figure 6, a larger proportion of participants rated the AV condition as providing better control for both direction (72%) and distance (69%), while relatively few participants favored the VR condition (6% for direction, 11% for distance), suggesting that participants subjectively perceived the AV condition as more favorable for putting control.

To examine preference, participants were asked to rank the three conditions by ordering them. The RW condition was ranked first by 77.78%, second by 16.67%, and third by 5.56% of the participants (mean rank 1.28). The AV condition was ranked first by 16.67%, second by 66.67%, and third by 16.67% (mean rank 2.0). Finally, the VR condition was ranked first by 5.56%, second by 16.67%, and third by 77.78% (mean rank 2.72).

5.6 Distance Estimation

When completing the RW condition, participants were asked to estimate the putt distance (ball start position to center of the target). The mean was 2.3 m ($SD = 0.43$). The real putting distance was 2.13 m (7 feet). No statistically significant correlation was found between the estimated distance and self-reported putting skill ($r = 0.095, p = 0.58$ and $\rho = 0.18, p = 0.28$).

6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Superiority of RW Putting Performance (H1)

Hypothesis H1 predicted superior putting performance in the real world (RW) compared to both augmented virtuality (AV) and virtual reality (VR). The results partially support this hypothesis. RW putting (57.5%) yielded a significantly higher holed percentage than VR (47.4%), but not than AV (56.3%). Thus, H1 is supported only insofar as RW outperformed VR, while RW and AV did not differ significantly.

Covariates captured meaningful individual differences. Participants with higher self-rated putting skill showed greater holed odds, and a modest within-condition learning effect emerged across the ten putts. The reported estimated marginal means reflect adjustment for these covariates (i.e., the expected performance of an average participant with random effects set to zero). These results confirm that the models accounted for relevant variance, but also indicate that condition

differences diminished once ability and learning were considered.

The similarity between RW and AV suggests that access to a real putter and ball, combined with visibility of the user's limbs through the passthrough window, restored critical alignment and distance cues. This interpretation is supported by the comparable NASA-TLX profiles of RW and AV. While prior work suggested RW defines the upper bound of performance [5, 16, 44], the small gap observed here indicates that AV can substantially narrow this boundary.

Simulator sickness further distinguished the conditions. VR produced significantly higher SSQ scores than RW across all dimensions, while AV scores were closer to RW. Notably, RW putting appeared to reduce symptoms relative to baseline, as indicated by negative SSQ deltas. These findings align with prior reports that sensory inconsistencies in VR contribute to both discomfort and degraded performance [16, 17].

Finally, several participants reported that distances between the ball and hole felt shorter in VR and AV than in RW. This underestimation of egocentric distance is a well-documented HMD effect [35] and has also been observed in previous virtual putting studies [16]. These findings highlight that even in AV, careful calibration of scale and depth cues remains essential, and residual miscalibration may explain why AV performance, task load, and user preference did not fully reach RW levels.

6.2 Superiority of AV over VR (H2)

Hypothesis H2 predicted that putting performance would be superior in AV compared to VR. The objective putting performance results support this hypothesis. Participants achieved significantly higher holed percentages in the physical tracked ball dataset and smaller mean miss distances in the simulated dataset in AV than in VR. Miss distances were reduced in AV (VR/AV ratio = 1.29), and holed probability was higher by 13.9 percentage points (EMMs: 0.296 in VR vs. 0.435 in AV, OR = 0.55). Notably, the AV advantage in holed percentage grew with participants' golf training frequency (Condition \times Training Frequency interaction), suggesting that experienced golfers benefited most from AV. These effects mirrored the direction of the ball-tracking results for holed percentage and further demonstrated an AV advantage for miss distance.

Participant feedback helps explain this advantage. Many reported that seeing the real putter head, hands, and feet through the passthrough cutout improved alignment, distance control, and confidence (e.g., "It was much easier for me to coordinate the putter, arms, ball and stroke"). By contrast, VR participants more often noted difficulty judging direction and speed (e.g., "hard to judge the direction and speed of the ball"). These remarks reinforce the quantitative results and highlight specific cues, including self-representation and visibility of the real putter, which AV restores to narrow the performance gap. Some trade-offs were also reported: the cutout edge could be exploited to align strokes, and real-world noises (e.g., ball-hole contact) occasionally distracted attention. These comments suggest refinements are needed for future simulation designs.

This simulation design builds on earlier putting studies that emphasized the role of high-fidelity haptics via real golf equipment [5, 10, 16]. The integration of a passthrough cutout for enhanced self-visualization and realism was motivated by prior recommendations [10, 16] and AV studies in other domains [6, 42, 43]. The present results show that combining high-fidelity haptics with selective passthrough effectively bridges the gap between RW and VR performance, yielding significantly better outcomes in AV than in VR and comparable outcomes between AV and RW.

6.3 Task Load and User Preference (H3)

H3 predicted that participants would experience higher task load and lower preference in VR compared to RW and AV. The results support this hypothesis. NASA-TLX profiles showed that RW and AV were similar, while VR involved higher mental demand and lower perceived performance. VR also elevated physical demand and frustration relative to RW, as shown in Figure 4. In line with these patterns, participants ranked RW and AV above VR in overall preference.

These results align with prior evidence that AV reduces workload by grounding interaction in real-world elements relevant to the task [6]. Participant comments reflect this contrast. In AV, one participant noted that "it helped that the putter was real and that I could also see my own body," illustrating how reduced cognitive load supported more fluid execution. In VR, others reported the opposite experience: "I felt more immersed in the virtual world [...], but I felt that my performance was not the best," showing the dissociation between immersion and effective task performance. Such elevated demands likely contributed to VR's lower performance outcomes, reinforcing the interpretation that task load mediates the performance gap.

In summary, AV reduced user's task load during putting in the VE, achieving the proposed "sweet spot" between realism and presence. RW and AV were comparable across subjective measures, whereas VR stood apart with higher workload and lower preference. This further explains the superior performance of AV over VR observed in H2.

6.4 Presence and Realism (H4)

H4 predicted that participants would report higher presence and perceived putting realism in AV than in VR. Contrary to this prediction, self-reported IPQ scores did not differ significantly between conditions (see supplementary material for detailed mean values across the IPQ subscales). This finding diverges from prior reports of AV benefits for presence in other domains [42, 43]. One possible explanation is a ceiling effect: both conditions already provided strong spatial grounding, either through the lower-body avatar in VR or visibility of the participant's own lower body in AV. Another factor may be measurement sensitivity: the IPQ was not designed for passthrough AR/AV scenarios and may miss nuances of these hybrid experiences [24, 39]. Therefore, H4 is not supported, indicating comparable levels of presence in VR and AV.

Mean scores for general presence and spatial presence were in the positive range (3–6), suggesting a solid sense of presence in both conditions, whereas involvement and realism scored lower. For involvement, participant feedback suggests that attention was occasionally drawn to real-world sounds (e.g., the ball falling into the cup or hitting platform boundaries). Domain-specific measures may thus be needed to capture the realism of such multisensory interactions. Indeed, while the IPQ realism subscale did not differ significantly, custom post-questionnaire items revealed significantly higher perceived realism in AV. Free-text remarks pointed to the congruence of the real putter, ball, and visible limbs as enhancing coordination and confidence (e.g., "no ambiguity between the real and virtual putter" and "I felt safer when I could see my [real] feet"). The additional weight of the attached controller was not generally perceived as distracting, suggesting that the tracking hardware did not compromise the experience.

Although AV did not exceed VR in IPQ presence, qualitative data and custom measures suggest that AV offered a more grounded experience. At the same time, AV induced fewer simulator sickness symptoms, yielding patterns more similar to RW than to VR. This likely reflects the visual and proprioceptive consistency afforded by passthrough, which can reduce disorientation and oculomotor strain. Together, these findings indicate that the AV condition successfully balanced sensory fidelity and immersion, maintaining presence while also enhancing realism and comfort.

6.5 Trade-offs and Generalizability of AV Training

A key advantage of the AV system is its ability to extend practice beyond the constraints of physical space while retaining critical real-world sensory cues, such as the feel of the putter, ball, and limb positioning. This benefit comes with a trade-off: minor simulation inaccuracies between the Quest 3 tracking system and real-world ball positions introduce small positional errors (mean absolute difference 0.046m for putts under 0.4m). Our results suggest that, for precision-based tasks like golf putting, these errors are small relative to the training gains afforded by AV and do not appear to compromise learning or user experience within the pilot study. However, because the physical platform limited the range of real putts, these discrepancies may be slightly underestimated. Practically, this indicates that AV can provide

a high-fidelity alternative when physical space is limited, though careful calibration and validation of the simulation remain important to minimize discrepancies.

While the present study focuses on golf putting as a case study, the findings are likely generalizable to other skill-based, precision-oriented sports where haptic feedback, visual alignment, and spatial perception are critical (e.g., darts, billiards, bowling, or table tennis). The design principle of selectively integrating real objects and body parts into a virtual environment to preserve embodiment and performance can guide the development of AV training systems in these domains. In particular, sports with constrained training spaces or high equipment costs stand to benefit from AV's ability to decouple physical space from virtual practice areas. Future work should investigate these extensions, systematically evaluate task-specific calibration requirements, and study how AV training impacts skill acquisition, retention, and transfer in diverse sports contexts.

6.6 Limitations and Future Work

This study provides meaningful insights into MR golf putting, but several limitations affect interpretation and generalizability. Each limitation also suggests opportunities for future work.

Physical space constraints. The size of the putting platform limited the range of real-world putts, as balls that rolled beyond its boundary were stopped. As a result, we only compared the mean absolute miss distance between AV and VR conditions using the Quest 3 simulation dataset, while the physical tracking dataset was filtered and used to calculate the simulation accuracy. While this may have underestimated the true error distribution compared to simulation, the AV approach still enabled participants to experience realistic spatial and alignment cues beyond the physical boundaries, supporting effective skill practice. Future work could use larger platforms to capture unconstrained putting and further refine RW-simulation comparisons.

Tracking fidelity. Occasional VR controller glitches produced unrealistically high ball velocities, requiring 11 putts (1.53%) to be removed. Minor positional mismatches between real and simulated balls also occurred, likely due to tracking inaccuracies, calibration drift, or physics modeling. These issues sometimes reduced immersion, for example when real ball sounds did not align with simulation visuals. Future research should improve robustness through advanced tracking systems, refined calibration, and enhanced physics, while integrating aligned audiovisual cues to minimize incongruence.

Limited full-body avatar tracking. Prior work has shown that full-body avatars can enhance embodiment, immersion, and task performance [1]. In our system, stance-related positioning cues were provided through a simplified lower-body avatar in VR. Notably, current software-based full-body tracking solutions (e.g., Meta's movement SDK [29]) primarily rely on pose estimation and animation rather than direct sensing of foot motion, which may not provide sufficiently accurate foot placement cues for precision sports such as golf putting. Future work should therefore investigate the integration of dedicated foot-tracking sensors or hybrid tracking pipelines to better capture lower-body kinematics and to systematically study how accurate foot motion representation affects embodiment, performance, and skill transfer in immersive sports training.

Design choices. Construct validity may have been affected by the rectangular passthrough window in AV, which provided incidental alignment cues absent in VR, and by the simplified VR avatar that reduced spatial awareness and embodiment. Future work should test different passthrough geometries, systematically balance visual cues across conditions, and incorporate fully tracked avatars to strengthen comparability and embodiment.

Limited number of trials. Participants performed only ten putts per condition, which represents a relatively low number of trials. This was primarily due to time constraints and the within-subjects design, which required completing multiple conditions in a single session. While a higher number of trials could provide more stable performance estimates, similar studies in VR golf putting have employed comparable trial counts in prior studies. For example, Franzluebbers and Johnsen [10] used three practice and six recorded putts per condition

per distance, and Harris et al. [16] used three practice and ten recorded putts per condition. Nevertheless, we acknowledge that coincidence or variability in individual putts could have influenced the results, and future work could increase the number of trials to improve measurement reliability.

Extending evaluation to golfers with more diverse putting conditions and expertise. The study included a diverse sample of non-golfers and intermediate players ($N = 36$), supporting broad applicability of the findings. While professional golfers were not tested and only a single flat putt distance was used, the setup still captured relevant skill-based behaviors for a wide population. In addition, we used a standard putter with a length of 86 cm for all participants, which may not have been optimal for every individual, as putter length and design can influence comfort, stance, and swing dynamics. Future work could address these limitations by including professional players, varying putter types and lengths, and systematically manipulating task difficulty through different putting distances and slopes to examine how training effects interact with task demands, as well as to study skill acquisition, retention, and transfer across conditions.

Overall, despite these constraints, the simulation offered a realistic representation of putting and demonstrated the benefits of combining haptic realism with AV techniques. Extending these methods to diverse tasks and populations, as well as to other sports and domains, will advance the development of MR training systems as hardware capabilities improve.

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, we examined golf putting performance across the reality-virtuality continuum, focusing on whether AV can enhance precision skill-based sports simulations compared to conventional VR and RW baselines. Our findings demonstrate clear benefits of AV over VR in both performance and user experience, while leveraging the immersive advantages of unbounded physical space. By preserving VR's flexibility and reintroducing critical real-world cues (hands, feet, putter, and ball), AV narrowed the gap to RW without compromising presence. Overall, AV emerges as a practical approach to balance sensory fidelity with immersive flexibility in skill-based sports training: improving putting accuracy and experience beyond VR, while approaching RW performance under controlled conditions.

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REFERENCES

- [1] A. Bartl, C. Merz, D. Roth, and M. E. Latoschik. The effects of avatar and environment design on embodiment, presence, activation, and task load in a virtual reality exercise application. *2022 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*, pp. 260–269, 2022. 9
- [2] P. Bimberg, T. Weissker, and A. Kulik. On the Usage of the Simulator Sickness Questionnaire for Virtual Reality Research. In *2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*, pp. 464–467, Mar. 2020. doi: 10.1109/VRW50115.2020.00098 6
- [3] L. J. Briggs. *Methods for Measuring the Coefficient of Restitution and the Spin of a Ball*. US Department of Commerce, National Bureau of Standards, 1945. 4
- [4] M. Broadie. *Every Shot Counts: Using the Revolutionary Strokes Gained Approach to Improve Your Golf Performance and Strategy*. Avery, New York, Mar. 2014. 2, 5
- [5] K. Brock, S. J. Vine, J. M. Ross, M. Trevarthen, and D. J. Harris. Movement kinematic and postural control differences when performing a visuomotor skill in real and virtual environments. *Experimental Brain Research*, 241(7):1797–1810, July 2023. doi: 10.1007/s00221-023-06639-0 1, 2, 4, 8

- [6] F. Chiossi, Y. El Khaoudi, C. Ou, L. Sidenmark, A. Zaky, T. Feuchtnr, and S. Mayer. Evaluating Typing Performance in Different Mixed Reality Manifestations using Physiological Features. *Proc. ACM Hum.-Comput. Interact.*, 8(ISS):542:377–542:406, Oct. 2024. doi: 10.1145/3698142 2, 3, 4, 8
- [7] S. A. Drew, M. F. Awad, J. A. Armendariz, B. Gabay, I. J. Lachica, and J. W. Hinkel-Lipsker. The Trade-Off of Virtual Reality Training for Dart Throwing: A Facilitation of Perceptual-Motor Learning With a Detriment to Performance. *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 2, May 2020. doi: 10.3389/fspor.2020.00059 1, 2
- [8] P. Düring, H.-C. Holmberg, and B. Sperlich. The Potential Usefulness of Virtual Reality Systems for Athletes: A Short SWOT Analysis. *Frontiers in Physiology*, 9, Mar. 2018. doi: 10.3389/fphys.2018.00128 2
- [9] Foresight Sports. Foresight Sports: Portable Golf Launch Simulators & Monitors. <https://www.foresightsports.com/>. 4
- [10] A. Franzluebbers and K. Johnsen. Performance Benefits of High-Fidelity Passive Haptic Feedback in Virtual Reality Training. In *Proceedings of the 2018 ACM Symposium on Spatial User Interaction*, SUI '18, pp. 16–24. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Oct. 2018. doi: 10.1145/3267782.3267790 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 9
- [11] M. Geisen, A. Nicklas, T. Baumgartner, and S. Klatt. Extended Reality as a Training Approach for Visual Real-Time Feedback in Golf. *IEEE Transactions on Learning Technologies*, 17:642–652, 2024. doi: 10.1109/TLT.2023.3322660 3
- [12] A. Godse, R. Khadka, and A. Banic. Evaluation of Visual Perception Manipulation in Virtual Reality Training Environments to Improve Golf Performance. In *2019 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces (VR)*, pp. 1807–1812, Mar. 2019. doi: 10.1109/VR.2019.8798026 2
- [13] R. Gray. Transfer of Training from Virtual to Real Baseball Batting. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 8, Dec. 2017. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2017.02183 1, 2
- [14] R. Gray. Virtual environments and their role in developing perceptual-cognitive skills in sports. In *Anticipation and Decision Making in Sport*. Routledge, 2019. 2
- [15] GWiz. Quest 3 Golf attachment by GWiz | Download free STL model. <https://www.printables.com/model/808999-quest-3-golf-attachment>. 3, 5
- [16] D. J. Harris, G. Buckingham, M. R. Wilson, J. Brookes, F. Mushtaq, M. Mon-Williams, and S. J. Vine. Exploring sensorimotor performance and user experience within a virtual reality golf putting simulator. *Virtual Reality*, 25(3):647–654, Sept. 2021. doi: 10.1007/s10055-020-00480-4 1, 2, 4, 5, 8, 9
- [17] D. J. Harris, G. Buckingham, M. R. Wilson, and S. J. Vine. Virtually the same? How impaired sensory information in virtual reality may disrupt vision for action. *Experimental Brain Research*, 237(11):2761–2766, Nov. 2019. doi: 10.1007/s00221-019-05642-8 1, 2, 8
- [18] S. G. Hart and L. E. Staveland. Development of NASA-TLX (Task Load Index): Results of Empirical and Theoretical Research. In P. A. Hancock and N. Meshkati, eds., *Advances in Psychology*, vol. 52 of *Human Mental Workload*, pp. 139–183. North-Holland, Jan. 1988. doi: 10.1016/S0166-4115(08)62386-9 5
- [19] J. Hoffard, T. Nakamura, E. Wu, and H. Koike. PushToSki - An Indoor Ski Training System Using Haptic Feedback. In *ACM SIGGRAPH 2021 Posters*, SIGGRAPH '21, pp. 1–2. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, Aug. 2021. doi: 10.1145/3450618.3469158 2
- [20] C. P. Hoffmann, A. Filippeschi, E. Ruffaldi, and B. G. Bardy. Energy management using virtual reality improves 2000-m rowing performance. *Journal of Sports Sciences*, 32(6):501–509, Apr. 2014. doi: 10.1080/02640414.2013.835435 1
- [21] Igroup. Igroup presence questionnaire (IPQ) Database | igroup.org – project consortium. <https://www.igroup.org/pq/ipq/data.php>. 7
- [22] R. S. Kennedy, N. E. Lane, K. S. Berbaum, and M. G. Lilienthal. Simulator Sickness Questionnaire: An Enhanced Method for Quantifying Simulator Sickness. *The International Journal of Aviation Psychology*, 3(3):203–220, July 1993. doi: 10.1207/s15327108ijap0303_3 5, 6
- [23] Kiri. KIRI Engine: 3D Scanner App for iPhone, Android, and Web. <https://www.kiriengine.app/>. 3
- [24] K. Li, S. Schmidt, R. Bacher, W. P. Leemans, and F. Steinicke. Mixed reality tunneling effects for stereoscopic untethered video-see-through head-mounted displays. *2022 IEEE International Symposium on Mixed and Augmented Reality (ISMAR)*, pp. 44–53, 2022. 4, 8
- [25] C.-C. Liao, Z. Yu, and H. Koike. Shiftinggolf: Gross motor skill correction using redirection in vr. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 31:3429–3439, 2025. 2
- [26] I. Mahalil, A. M. Yusof, and N. Ibrahim. A literature review on the usage of Technology Acceptance Model for analysing a virtual reality's cycling sport applications with enhanced realism fidelity. In *2020 8th International Conference on Information Technology and Multimedia (ICIMU)*, pp. 237–242, Aug. 2020. doi: 10.1109/ICIMU49871.2020.9243571 1
- [27] Meta. Developing extended reality apps for Horizon OS in Unity. <https://developers.meta.com/horizon/documentation/unity/unity-development-overview/>. 3, 4
- [28] Meta. Meta Quest 3: Mixed-Reality-VR-Headset. <https://www.meta.com/de/quest/quest-3/>. 3
- [29] Meta Platforms, Inc. *Meta Movement SDK Overview*. Meta for Developers. 9
- [30] P. Milgram and F. Kishino. A Taxonomy of Mixed Reality Visual Displays. *IEICE Transactions on Information and Systems*, Dec. 1994. 1, 2, 3
- [31] T. Nakamura, D. Saito, E. Wu, and H. Koike. Actuated club: Modification of golf-club posture with force feedback and motion prediction in vr environment. *ACM SIGGRAPH 2020 Emerging Technologies*, 2020. 2
- [32] D. L. Neumann, R. L. Moffitt, P. R. Thomas, K. Loveday, D. P. Watling, C. L. Lombard, S. Antonova, and M. A. Tremeer. A systematic review of the application of interactive virtual reality to sport. *Virtual Reality*, 22(3):183–198, Sept. 2018. doi: 10.1007/s10055-017-0320-5 2
- [33] H. Oagaz, B. Schoun, and M.-H. Choi. Performance Improvement and Skill Transfer in Table Tennis Through Training in Virtual Reality. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 28(12):4332–4343, Dec. 2022. doi: 10.1109/TVCG.2021.3086403 2
- [34] Y. Okada, C. Seo, S. Miyakawa, M. Taniguchi, K. Kanosue, H. Ogata, and J. Ohya. Virtual Ski Training System that Allows Beginners to Acquire Ski Skills Based on Physical and Visual Feedbacks. In *2023 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*, pp. 1268–1275, Oct. 2023. doi: 10.1109/IROS55552.2023.10342020 2
- [35] R. S. Renner, B. M. Velichkovsky, and J. R. Helmer. The perception of egocentric distances in virtual environments - A review. *ACM Comput. Surv.*, 46(2):23:1–23:40, Dec. 2013. doi: 10.1145/2543581.2543590 5, 8
- [36] F. Richlan, M. Weiß, P. Kastner, and J. Braid. Virtual training, real effects: A narrative review on sports performance enhancement through interventions in virtual reality. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, Oct. 2023. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1240790 2
- [37] T. W. Schubert. The sense of presence in virtual environments: A three-component scale measuring spatial presence, involvement, and realism. *Zeitschrift für Medienpsychologie*, 15(2):69–71, 2003. doi: 10.1026/1617-6383.15.2.69 5, 7
- [38] R. Skarbez, M. Smith, and M. C. Whitton. Revisiting Milgram and Kishino's Reality-Virtuality Continuum. *Frontiers in Virtual Reality*, 2, Mar. 2021. doi: 10.3389/frvir.2021.647997 3
- [39] T. Q. Tran, T. Langlotz, and H. Regenbrecht. A Survey On Measuring Presence in Mixed Reality. In *Proceedings of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems*, pp. 1–38. ACM, Honolulu HI USA, May 2024. doi: 10.1145/3613904.3642383 8
- [40] Unity Technologies. Unity Real-Time Development Platform | 3D, 2D, VR & AR Engine. <https://unity.com>. 3
- [41] Viewlicity GmbH. PuttView - Upgrade your Game. <https://www.puttview.com/>. 3
- [42] A. Villegas, P. Perez, R. Kachach, F. Pereira, and E. Gonzalez-Sosa. Realistic training in VR using physical manipulation. In *2020 IEEE Conference on Virtual Reality and 3D User Interfaces Abstracts and Workshops (VRW)*, pp. 109–118, Mar. 2020. doi: 10.1109/VRW50115.2020.00025 2, 3, 4, 5, 8
- [43] K. Waldow, C. Kleinbeck, A. Fuhrmann, and D. Roth. Investigating the Impact of Video Pass-Through Embodiment on Presence and Performance in Virtual Reality. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 31(5):2364–2373, May 2025. doi: 10.1109/TVCG.2025.3549891 2, 3, 4, 5, 8
- [44] K. Witte, D. Bürger, and S. Pastel. Sports training in virtual reality with a focus on visual perception: A systematic review. *Frontiers in Sports and Active Living*, 7, Mar. 2025. doi: 10.3389/fspor.2025.1530948 1, 2, 8
- [45] E. Wu, M. Piekenbrock, T. Nakamura, and H. Koike. SPinPong - Virtual Reality Table Tennis Skill Acquisition using Visual, Haptic and Temporal Cues. *IEEE Transactions on Visualization and Computer Graphics*, 27(5):2566–2576, May 2021. doi: 10.1109/TVCG.2021.3067761 2